

10th ICFA Beam Dynamics Panel WORKSHOP
4th Generation Light Sources
Grenoble, January 22-25, 1996

Design of a Diffraction Limited Light Source (DIFL)

(Grenoble – ESRF-Paper)

D. Einfeld, J. Schaper, Fachhochschule Ostfriesland, Constantiaplatz 4, D-
26723 Emden

M. Plesko, Institute Jozef Stefan, Jamova 39, P.O.B. 100, SLO-61111 Ljubljana
e-mail: einfeld@alpha.fho-emden.de

Abstract:

A lot of synchrotron light sources (SLS) of the third generation have been commissioned (ESRF, ALS, ELETTRA, APS, PLS, SRRC). All machines have reached their target specifications (emittance ≈ 6 nrad, current ≈ 200 mA etc) without any problems. Hence it should be possible to run light sources with a smaller emittance to get a higher brilliance and emitting coherent radiation. The brilliance of a 4th generation light source should be determined by diffraction effects and not by the cross section of the beam. A design of a Diffraction Limited Light Source (DIFL) has been performed. It is a 3 GeV storage ring which is comprised of a DBA-structure with 4 degree bending magnets and alternatively a modified multiple bend achromat (MBA) optics as a lattice leading to a normalized emittance of $\epsilon_{x,y} = 0.5$ nrad. The novel feature of this MBA-lattice is the use of horizontally defocussing bending magnets with different bending angles to keep the radiation integrals low. The circumference is 400 m including 12 straight sections with a length of 6 m. The dynamical behaviour should allow to store a beam of 100 mA with a lifetime larger than 3 hours.

I. INTRODUCTION

The spectral brilliance is more or less the figure of merit for synchrotron radiation users. It is defined as [1]:

$$Bl = \frac{Fl}{4\pi^2 \Sigma_x \Sigma'_x \Sigma_y \Sigma'_y} \quad [1]$$

$\Sigma_{x,y}$ and $\Sigma'_{x,y}$ are the overall cross section and the divergence respectively of the beam (see table 1 with some formulae for the calculation of the brilliance). The flux of the radiation from an undulator can be expressed as [1][2]:

$$Fl(n) = A_n(K) \cdot N \cdot (I / A) \quad [2]$$

The on-axis peak energy of emitted radiation from the undulator is factorized by [3]:

$$E_\gamma(n) = D_n(K) \cdot \frac{(E / GeV)^2}{(\lambda_u / cm)} \quad [3]$$

The definitions of the symbols are given in table 1. The graph $A_n(K)$ as a function of $D_n(K)$ is presented in Fig.1 for the harmonics $n = 1, 3, 5$ and 7 . With this curve it is very easy to calculate the brilliance as a function of photon energies for different light sources and undulators. It can be taken as a normalized brilliance curve for undulators.

In the event that the radiation cross section σ_r (see table 1 and 2) can be ignored, the brilliance of the radiation from an undulator is determined by the emittance ϵ_{x0} (see table1) of the electron beam:

$$Bl = \frac{Fl}{4\pi^2 \kappa \epsilon_{x0}^2} = A_n(K) \cdot \frac{N \cdot (I / A)}{4\pi^2 \kappa \epsilon_{x0}^2} \quad [4]$$

With the dependence of the emittance upon the energy of the storage ring $\epsilon_{x0} = \epsilon^* \cdot \gamma^2$ the brilliance decreases with the 4th power of the energy E:

$$Bl(n) = A_n(K) \cdot \frac{N \cdot (I / A)}{4\pi^2 \kappa (\epsilon^*)^2 \gamma^4} \quad [5]$$

and according to Eq.3 the photon energy increases with the 2nd power of the energy. According to Eq.5 one might assume that for achieving very high brilliances ultra low emittances should be envisaged. However, taking diffraction into account, at very low emittances the brilliance does not scale that way, the brilliance leads to a limit. Light sources running at this limits are "diffraction limited light sources".

A simple explanation for this limit can be given by tracing the path of the electron beam through the undulator and take into account the opening angle of the synchrotron radiation. The path of the electron beam through the undulator in a first approximation is a sine curve [3]:

$$X = X_0 \sin\left(2\pi \frac{s}{\lambda_u}\right) \quad [6]$$

X_0 is the amplitude and λ_u is the period of the undulator. The limit of the brilliance is reached when the cross section of the electron beam is smaller than the amplitude of the sine curve according to Eq.6 (see table 2.), i.e. when the emittance of the electron beam equals the emittance of the radiated beam. Taking the half opening angle (for the critical photon energy) of the synchrotron radiation from bending magnets [4]:

$$\psi_{1/2} = 0.626 \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma} \approx \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma} \quad [7]$$

the so called photon emittance results in:

$$\varepsilon_{phot} \approx X_0 \cdot \psi_{1/2} \approx \frac{K\lambda_u}{4\pi\gamma^2} \quad [8]$$

From Eq.8 the photon emittance is a function of the characteristics of the undulator (K and λ_u) and the electron energy E ($\gamma = E/m_0c^2 = 1957 \cdot (E/\text{GeV})^2$).

The results of the exact theory of the undulator radiation [1][3][5] are summarized in table 2. According to this the photon emittance of an undulator is:

$$\varepsilon_{phot} = \sigma_{ph} \cdot \rho_{ph} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \lambda \quad [9]$$

λ is the wavelength of the radiation from the undulator. With the dependence of the wavelength λ on the characteristics of the undulator (see table 2) the correct photon emittance is:

$$\varepsilon_{ph} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{\lambda_u}{\gamma^2} \cdot \frac{(1 + \frac{K^2}{2})}{2n} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{K\lambda_u}{\gamma^2} \cdot \frac{(\frac{1}{K} + \frac{K}{2})}{2n} \quad [10]$$

$$= 2.078 \cdot 10^{-4} \frac{(\lambda_u / cm)}{[E / GeV]^2} \cdot \frac{(1 + \frac{K^2}{2})}{2 \cdot n} mm \cdot mrad \quad [11]$$

The last part in Eq.10 is the correction to the simple formula in Eq.8. For the undulators the K-value is typically between 0.5/1.0/2.0 to 5.0. With these values the correction term for the fundamental harmonics changes from 1.125 / 0.75 / 1.25 to 1.35.

Combining the equations [10] / [11] and [1] / [2] the brilliance of the undulator radiation of a diffraction limited light source can be calculated as:

$$Bl(n) = 2.347 \cdot 10^6 \frac{A_n(K)N(I / A) \cdot (E / GeV)^4 \cdot n^2}{(\lambda_u / cm)^2 \cdot (1 + \frac{K^2}{2})^2} \quad [12]$$

Hence the brilliance of a diffraction limited light source increases with the fourth power of the energy of the electrons in the case the characteristics (K and λ_u) of the undulator are kept constant. This is quite different from the "normal" light sources (see Eq.5). For synchrotron radiation users it is more convenient to express the brilliance as a function of the photon energy: With the flux FI from the undulator (according to Eq. [2]) it follows that the brilliance of the harmonic n measured in [photons / (sec 0.1%BW mm² mrad²)] is:

$$Bl_n(K) = 2.606 \cdot 10^6 \cdot A_n(K) \cdot N \cdot (I / A) \cdot [E_\gamma(n)]^2 \quad [13]$$

With the values: K=2.0, $A_1(2.0)=1.4 \cdot 10^{14}$, L=3.2m, $\lambda_u=3.2$ cm, N=100 and I=0.2A we get as an example:

$$Bl(1) = 7.3 \cdot 10^{21} \cdot [E_{ph}(1) / keV]^2 \quad [14]$$

Fig.2 shows the brilliance of a diffraction limited light source (Eq.14) in comparison to the ESRF (6 GeV) [6], NSLS (2.5 GeV) [7] and ELETTRA (2 GeV) [8] all running with a current of 200 mA and an emittance

coupling of 2 %, implying that the brilliance could be increased by three orders of magnitudes the undulator characteristics for these curves are the same one as for Eq. 13 and 14. At present there doesn't exist a 3rd generation light source with an energy around 3 GeV but there are some proposals, e.g. ROSY II [9].

For a 3 GeV light source, the typical undulator radiation peaks at a wavelength of around 1 nm, or an energy of 1.2 keV, respectively. This means that for a diffraction limited light source, according to Eq. [8], the emittance would have to be below 0.08 nm·rad. Take into account the coupling factor $K=1$ the normalized emittance of a diffraction limited light source has to be $\epsilon_{x0} = 0.16$ nm rad.

The third generation light sources ESRF, ALS and ELETTRA have been commissioned in record times and are running very well and reliable. This proves that it should be possible to obtain a horizontal emittance which is an order of magnitude below the present one of these machines, i.e. around 0.5 nm·rad. With a coupling of 1%, the corresponding vertical emittance is 5 pm·rad. The diffraction limited emittance would thus be between the two values. The goal is to design a 3 GeV synchrotron light source with a natural emittance of 0.5 nm·rad. In that case, at least the vertical emittance of that radiation is diffraction limited.

It is interesting to note that damping rings for the next generation electron-positron colliders have a similar emittance and a similar particle energy [10]. They can be kept much more compact, however, because the light sources need a larger circumference to accommodate straight sections for insertion devices.

2. OBTAINING A LOW EMITTANCE

As lattices for storage rings and synchrotron light sources the FODO-, DBA-, TBA- and TME-structures (theoretical minimum emittance) are well known [11][12][13]. With the exception of the TME-structure all other types have been used in existing machines [7]. The emittance of each lattice can be characterized by the expression:

$$\epsilon_{x0} = C_q \cdot \gamma^2 \cdot \frac{1}{J_x} \cdot K \cdot \frac{1}{3 \cdot 4 \sqrt{15}} \cdot \varphi^3 \quad [15]$$

$C_q = 3.84 \cdot 10^{-13}$, $\gamma = 1957 \cdot (E/\text{GeV})^2$, $J_x =$ Partition function, $\varphi =$ deflection angle of the bending magnet and K is the quality factor of the lattice. For cost reduction the deflection angle should be as high as possible (lowering the numbers of magnets) hence the K -value should be small.

The FODO-structure [14] has been suggested for a damping ring with a deflection angle of 0.9743 degree per magnet and a phase advance per cell of 100 degrees. The emittance of this 4 GeV machine is 0.37 nm rad,

having a K-value of 150. With an optimization of the phase advance per cell [14] to 135 degrees the K-value can be reduced to 75. For a design of a 3 GeV damping ring [15] with 5 degree magnets the K-value is 242. PETRA at DESY with a FODO-structure is presently partly used for synchrotron radiation experiments [16]. With 1.607 degree bends and a K-value of 100 the energy dependence of the emittance is:

$$\varepsilon_{x0} = 6.98 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot (E / \text{Gev})^2 \text{ mrad} \quad [16]$$

At an energy of 3 GeV the emittance of PETRA is 0.6 nm*rad and it is a "diffraction limited light source". The circumference of PETRA is 2000 m. Overall it means that the FODO-structure is very uneconomical for a diffraction limited light source.

A good example for the DBA-structure is the ESRF-lattice [6][7]. This lattice at 6 GeV with 5.625 degree bends and without a hybrid structure results in an emittance of 6.8 nm*rad, leading to a K-value of 6.3. From the theoretical point of view [17] the minimum value of K is three. Different is the Elettra-design [8]. With a larger distance between the bendings in the dispersive region it is possible to have a minimum of the horizontal betatron function in this area leading to a smaller emittance. For ELETTRA the K-value is 4. According to the energy dependence of the emittance, at 3 GeV the ESRF would result in an emittance of 1.7 nm*rad, a factor 3.5 away from 0.5 nm*rad. To reach the 0.5 nm*rad the deflection angle has to be reduced to 3.57 degrees. That would increase the circumference to 1000 m.

The TME-structure [17][18] gives from the theoretical point of view the lowest emittance. In this case the theoretical K-value is 1. With a 20 degree deflection angle and a drift space of 2 m an emittance of 9.07 nm*rad could be reached. This results in a K-value of 1.14, which is the lowest value of all optics. The TME-structure applied to a 10 degree bending magnet yields at 3 GeV an emittance of 3.6 nm*rad. The corresponding optic is presented in Fig.3. In both examples (10 and 20 degrees) the magnets have a gradient resulting in a J_x -value of 1.2 to 1.5, which also helps to reduce the emittance. For the TME-structure the phase advance per cell is larger than π (4.0 to 4.5).

A simplification of the TME-structure can be reached by using only a focusing quadrupole in the long straight section and perform the defocusing with the bending magnet. Such a structure has been used for the proposed light sources ROSY I [19] and ROSY II [9]. This structure is given in Fig.4. With a 9 degree bending magnet it is possible to reach at 3 GeV an emittance of 3.16 nm*rad resulting in a K-Value of 4. With the φ^3 -dependence the deflection angle for a 0.5 nm*rad emittance source should be 5 degree.

As a conclusion it follows that a lattice of a 3 GeV diffraction limited light source should be built up with a DBA or TME-structure with some

advantages for the last one: the K-value is smaller, the deflection angle is larger and the structure is more compact.

3.) DBA-STRUCTURE AS A LATTICE FOR A DIFL

As a starting point a modified ESRF lattice is taken (Fig.5), optimized for undulators only, as we get no brilliance increase with wigglers. The working points are chosen to $Q_x=30.2$ and $Q_y=8.2$, in order to get a sufficient dynamic aperture of ± 50 mm in the horizontal and ± 40 mm in the vertical direction or a dynamic acceptance of $A_x= 91$ mm*mrad and $A_y= 140$ mm*mrad. The dispersion function has a maximum of 0.45 m and the radius of the bendings is $r=23.26$ m corresponding to a magnetic flux of $B_0=0.857$ T at $E=6$ GeV. The chromaticities are $\xi_x=-89$ and $\xi_y=-24$.

A modification of the lattice to 3 GeV with $B_0=1.0$ T and a maximum gradient in the quads of 17 T/m yields to an emittance of 1.85 nm*rad. But with a drastically reduced dynamic aperture down to ± 20 mm in the horizontal and ± 15 mm in the vertical direction corresponding to a dynamic aperture of $A_x= 130$ and $A_y= 74$ mm*mrad. The chromaticities in this case are $\xi_x=-135$ and $\xi_y=-29$. The maximum dispersion is reduced from 0.45 m to 0.32 m according to the lower radius. The higher chromaticities and the lower dispersion function are the reason that the dynamic aperture decreases so much. The higher chromaticities are due to the fact that the quadrupoles have been shortened but the distance between the quads have been kept constant. This leads to a higher strength of the quads.

With the same setup of magnets it is possible to run the machine with a TME-structure. Lowering the strength of the quads within the dispersive region the DBA-structure goes over to a TME-structure as shown in Fig.6. Sometimes this lattice is called a DBA-structure with a distributed dispersion function. In this case the emittance is reduced to 0.75nm*rad and the K-value is as low as 2.8. The dynamic aperture is not very large ± 24 mm in the horizontal and ± 12 mm in the vertical direction (Fig.6, below).

A disadvantage of this structure is the dispersion function in the straight section which increases the cross section of the beam and reduces the overall emittance. This amount can be estimated by the calculation of the factor (see Eq.1):

$$(4\pi^2 \sum_x \sum_x' \sum_y \sum_y')^{-1} \quad [17]$$

The results are: DBA $\equiv 3.86 \cdot 10^5$ and DBA-TME $\equiv 1.70 \cdot 10^6$. Hence with the distributed dispersion function the effective gain in brilliance is roughly fourfold.

With the wanted emittance for a DIFL of 0.5 nm*rad the deflection angle has to be reduced to 4 degree. For the DBA-structure this yields to an emittance of 0.94 nm*rad and for the DBA-TME of 0.3 nm*rad. The dynamical aperture however is very small, it goes down to 10 mm in the horizontal and 7.5 mm in the vertical direction (see fig.7). The dynamic apertures are below 10 mm*mrad. At the ESRF it was possible to run the machine very successful with acceptances of $A_x=3.6$ mm*mrad and $A_y=8.7$ mm*mrad

4. THE CONCEPTS OF THE MBA LATTICE FOR DIFL

The lattice of a multiple bend achromat (MBA) structure can be described as a set of several unit cells accompanied on each side by a matching section followed by a straight section, the places for the undulators. The matching sections assure that the dispersion is zero in the straight sections and that the beta-functions can be set to the requirements of either undulators (high beta) or wigglers (low beta). The dipoles within the unit cells have a deflection angle of φ , whereas the ones in the matching section deflect by $\varphi/2$.

The unit cell (see Fig.4) with a defocussing bending magnet has a threefold advantage:

- 1) the number of magnets per achromat is reduced;
- 2) the partition number J_x is larger than 1 and thus reduces the emittance (see Eq.15);
- 3) the length of the cell is small, therefore reducing the total circumference.

The circumference of such a machine containing five unit cells within an achromat which performs an overall deflection of 30 degrees would be around 400 m.

Accepting reasonable magnetic field strengths for the bending magnets determines more or less the length of the magnets. The only two free parameters which can be varied to minimize the emittance are the strength of the focusing quadrupole and the defocusing bending magnet. Therefore it is easy to find the optimal setting (Fig.8), resulting in an emittance of 0.47 nm·rad. The shape of the Twiss functions within a unit cell is shown in Fig 4.

The performance of the achromat is mainly determined by the unit cell. Its characteristics are given by the factors: emittance, partition number, working point, chromaticities and momentum compaction factor. The optimisation of the lattice is therefore first done on a hypothetical ring consisting of 72 unit cells. From Fig. 8 one can see, that the minimal emittance depends very weakly on the defocussing strength of the bend. Therefore it can be chosen such as to find an optics with a large dynamic

aperture by keeping the total tune away from dangerous resonances. The results of tracking one particle over 100 turns through the hypothetical ring are shown in Fig. 9. Only chromatic sextupoles have been used. The tracking has been performed using the computer codes RACETRACK [20] and BETA [21]. The dependence on the particle momentum is negligible.

The dynamic aperture is particularly large if one considers that it extends from -296 to 160 times the beam width in the horizontal plane and to +/-3680 times the beam height (at 1% coupling) in the vertical plane. Thus the overall dynamic properties of the MBA lattice are very promising. The optical functions for one achromat of the DIFL lattice. Indicated are the position and sizes of bending magnets and quadrupoles. All units are in meters.

5. THE DIFL LATTICE

In the realistic lattice, twelve straight sections of 6m length each are introduced, leaving sufficient space for insertion devices. Four quadrupoles and a 2.5 degree bending magnet compose the matching section to set the dispersion to zero and the horizontal and vertical beta functions in the straight sections to the desired values (Fig. 10).

With the matching, the emittance is increased by the presence of the outer two magnets from 0.47 nm rad to 0.56 nm rad. Assuming 2% coupling between planes, the beam sizes $\sigma_{x,y}$ are 54 μm and 5.8 μm in the horizontal and vertical plane, respectively. All damping times are around or below 9 ms, the relative energy spread is $8 \cdot 10^{-4}$, and even the natural chromaticities are not too large (-77 horizontal and -37 vertical).

Unfortunately, the dynamic aperture is reduced once the optics composed of unit cells only is modified to allow for dispersion-free straight sections. Even after reoptimizing the optics, the largest dynamic aperture obtained is 10 mm horizontally and 8 mm vertically (Fig 11), certainly creating a challenge for the injection into the ring but not rendering the optics unfeasible, because once the injected beam is damped to the natural emittance, the dynamic aperture still corresponds to more than 100 times the beam size in both planes. This should be sufficient to accommodate Touschek scattering given that the dispersion is also quite small.

The plot of the tune shift with amplitude (Fig. 12) reveals that indeed the dynamic aperture vanishes due to the rapid change of the tune. With proper sextupole arrangements we hope to increase the dynamic aperture to larger values.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The presented multiple bend achromat (MBA) lattice provides a mean to obtain significantly lower emittances than with conventional DBA or TBA lattices. The advantages of the modified lattice are the small

contribution of the outer magnets bending to the emittance, a large horizontal partition number which further reduces the emittance, a small number of quadrupole magnets, a short unit cell and good dynamic properties with only chromatic sextupoles. The scheme of the MBA optics can be applied to small compact rings as well as for the design of a diffraction limited light source. The layout of a DIFL with a twelvefold symmetry is given in Fig.13

7. REFERENCES

- [1] K.J.Kim, Characteristics of Synchrotron Radiation, X-RAY DATA BOOKLET, Lawrence Berkeley Laboratory, PUB-490 (1986).
- [2] S.L.Hubert and J.M.Weber, Flux and Brightness Calculations for Various Synchrotron Radiation Sources, NIM, A319 (1992) 25-31 and BNL-47034, Informal Report
- [3] P. Elleaume, CAS, Synchrotron Radiation and Free Electron Laser, CERN 90-03
- [4] S.Krinsky, M.L.Pearlman and R.E.Watson, Characteristics of Synchrotron Radiation and of its Sources, Handbook of Synchrotron Radiation, Vol. I, North Holland Publishing Company, 1983
- [5] H.Wiedemann, Particle Accelerator Physics II, Springer Verlag, 1995 ISBN 3-540-57564-2
- [6] ESRF - Foundation Phase Report, February 1987, European Synchrotron Radiation Facility, Grenoble, France
- [7] J.Murphy, Synchrotron Light Source Data Book, Version 3.0, October 1992, BNL 42333, Informal Report
- [8] ELETTRA, Conceptual Design Report, Sincrotrone Trieste, Padriciano 99, I 34012 Trieste, Italy
- [9] D.Einfeld and M.Plesko, The QBA Optics for the 3.2 GeV Synchrotron Light Source ROSY II, Proceedings of the Particle Accelerator Conference PAC 93, Washington, 1993.
- [10] R.Brinkmann, A Study of Low-Emittance Damping Ring Lattices, DESY, M-90-09, July 1990
- [11] A.Wrulich, Study of FODO Structures for Synchrotron Light Sources,

Particle Accelerators, 1988, Vol. 22, pp. 257-272

- [12] A.Roport, High Brilliance Lattices and the Effects of Insertion Devices, CERN 90 - 03, 158 (1990)
- [13] R. Maier, High Brilliance Lattices, CERN 89 - 01, 89 (1989)
- [14] L.Emery, Further Dynamic Aperture Studies on a Wiggler-Based Ultra-Low-Emittance Damping Ring Lattice, Particle Accelerator Conference, San Francisco, California, 6 - 9 May, 1991
- [14] J.Decking, DESY, Private Communication
- [15] Hasylab, Jahresbericht 1994
- [16] D.Einfeld and M.Plesko, A modified QBA optics for low emittance storage rings, NIM A335 (1993) 402-416
- [17] L.C.Teng, Minimum Emittance Lattice for Synchrotron Radiation Storage Rings, ANL / FNAL LS-17 (May 1985)
- [18] D.Einfeld et. al., The Synchrotron Light Source ROSY, NIM B89 (1994) 74-78
- [19] User's Guide, Sincrotrone Trieste, ST/M-91/11, F.lazzourene, C.J.Bocchetta, R.Nagaoka, L.Tosi, A.Wrulich, RACETRACK, July 1991
- [20] L.Farvacque, A.Roport, BETA User's Guide, ESRF-SR/LAT 88-08

$$B_n = \frac{Fl_n}{4\pi^2 \Sigma_x \Sigma_y \Sigma'_x \Sigma'_y} \quad [1]$$

$$\Sigma_x = \sqrt{\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_r^2}, \quad \Sigma_y = \sqrt{\sigma_y^2 + \sigma_r^2} \quad [2]$$

$$\Sigma'_x = \sqrt{\sigma_x'^2 + \sigma_r'^2}, \quad \Sigma'_y = \sqrt{\sigma_y'^2 + \sigma_r'^2} \quad [3]$$

$$\sigma_x = \sqrt{\varepsilon_x \beta_x + \sigma_E^2 \eta_x^2}, \quad \sigma_y = \sqrt{\varepsilon_y \beta_y} \quad [4]$$

$$\sigma'_x = \sqrt{\varepsilon_x \gamma_x + \sigma_E'^2 \eta_x'^2}, \quad \sigma'_y = \sqrt{\varepsilon_y \gamma_y} \quad [5]$$

$$\gamma_i = \frac{1 + \alpha_i^2}{\beta_i}, \quad \alpha_i = -\frac{1}{2} \beta_i', \quad \varepsilon_x = \frac{\varepsilon_{x0}}{1 + \kappa}, \quad \varepsilon_y = \frac{\kappa \varepsilon_{x0}}{1 + \kappa} \quad [6]$$

$$\begin{aligned} Fl_n &= 1.43 \cdot 10^{14} N Q_n(K) (I / \text{Amp}) \\ &= A_n(K) N (I / \text{Amp}) \frac{\text{Photons}}{s \cdot 0.1\%bw} \end{aligned} \quad [7]$$

$$Q_n(K) = \xi_n(K) \left\{ J_{\frac{n-1}{2}} \left[\frac{1}{4} \xi_n(K) \right] - J_{\frac{n+1}{2}} \left[\frac{1}{4} \xi_n(K) \right] \right\} \quad [8]$$

$$K = 0.934 (B_u / T) (\lambda_u / \text{cm}), \quad \xi_n(K) = n \frac{K^2}{\left(1 + \frac{K^2}{2}\right)} \quad [9]$$

σ_j : cross section of e-beam, σ_j' : divergence of e-beam, ε_j : emittance of e beam, ε_{x0} : normalized emittance, κ : coupling factor, σ_r : radiation cross section, σ_r' : radiation divergence, α_j , β_j , γ_j : twiss parameter of electron beam, $J(n-1/2), J(n+1/2)$: Bessel functions, B_u : maximum magnetic flux within the undulator, λ_u : period length of undulator, n : harmonic number

Table 1: Formulas for the calculation of the undulator radiation brilliance

$$B(s) = B_u \cdot \sin(2\pi s / \lambda_u) \quad [1]$$

$$X(s) = X_0 \cdot \sin(2\pi s / \lambda_u), \quad X'(s) = X_0' \cdot \cos(2\pi s / \lambda_u) \quad [2]$$

$$X_0 = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \cdot \frac{eB}{c} \cdot \lambda_u^2 = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \cdot \frac{\lambda_u^2}{\rho} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{K}{\gamma} \lambda_u \quad [3]$$

$$X_0' = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_u} \cdot X_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{\lambda_u}{\rho} = \frac{K}{\gamma} = K \cdot \Psi_{rad} \quad [4]$$

$$K = \frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{eB_u}{mc} \cdot \lambda_u = \frac{\gamma}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{\lambda_u}{\rho} \quad [5]$$

$$K = 0.934(B_u / T)(\lambda_u / cm), \quad \gamma = 1957(E / GeV) \quad [6]$$

$$\lambda_n(\text{axis}) = \frac{\lambda_u}{2n\gamma^2} \left(1 + \frac{K^2}{2}\right)_{n=1,3,5..} \quad [7]$$

$$E_n = \frac{n2\gamma^2 hc}{\lambda_u \left(1 + \frac{K^2}{2}\right)} = 0.949 keV (E / GeV)^2 \frac{n}{(\lambda_u / cm) \left(1 + \frac{K^2}{2}\right)} \quad [8]$$

$$\sigma_r = \frac{1}{4\pi} \sqrt{\lambda \cdot L_u}, \quad \sigma_r' = \sqrt{\lambda / L_u} \quad [9]$$

$$\varepsilon_{phot} = \sigma_r \sigma_r' = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} = 0.99 \frac{nm \cdot rad}{(E_n / keV)} \quad [10]$$

$$B_n(K) = 2.606 \cdot 10^6 A_n(K) N(I / Amp) \cdot [E_\gamma(n)]^2 \quad [11]$$

Table 2: Formulae connected with the movement of electrons through an undulator and the corresponding radiation.

Fig.1: The normalized function A_n for the description of the photon flux from an undulator as a function of the normalized photon energy D_n .

Fig.2: Brilliance of the undulator radiation by the installation of the same device ($Lu=3.2m$, $lu=3.2\text{ cm}$, $N=100$) in different storage rings, all running with a current of $I=200\text{ mA}$ and a coupling factor $a_0=2\%$. The brilliance of a diffraction limited light source is also shown. The emittances of the different machines are: NSLS XRAY: 100, ESRF: 6.8, ELETTRA: 7 and ROSY II: 2.8 nm \cdot rad.

Fig.3: Arrangement of magnets to reach the theoretical minimum emittance (TME-structure). The bending magnet performs a focusing in the vertical direction. For the deflection angle of 20 degree a K-value of 1.14 could be reach.

Fig.4: A simplified TME-structure existing of a defocusing bending magnet and a focusing quadrupole. The quality factor K for the lattice has a value around 4.

Fig. 6: The DBA-lattice changed to get a TME-structure in order to reduce the emittance of a factor 2. The dynamic aperture (below) is the same as for the poor DBA-structure (see fig.5).

Fig.7: Dynamic aperture for a lattice with a 4 degree bending magnet. Above the DBA-structure and below the DBA-TME structure, the dynamic acceptances are: DBA: $A_x=9.56$ and $A_y=25 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{mrad}$, DBA-TME: $A_x=2.5$ and $A_y=5.12 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{mrad}$.

DIFL

Fig 8: The emittance of the DIFL unit cell as a function of the focusing quadrupole strength at different defocusing strengths of the bending magnet. The minimum emittance for a 5 degree bending is 0.47 nm*rad.

Dynamische Apertur

Fig.9.: The dynamic aperture of the MBA lattice composed of unit cells only. The position of the Sh-sextupoles are at the beginning and end of the cell and that one of the Sv is 35 cm away from the edges of the bendings.

Fig.10: The optical functions for one achromat of the DIFL lattice.

Dynamische Apertur

Fig.11: The dynamic aperture of the DIFL lattice. The dynamic aperture expressed in beam sizes are: $X=100 \text{ sx}$ and $Y=750 \text{ sy}$. The dynamic acceptance are: $A_x= 20 \text{ mm}^*\text{mrad}$ and $A_y= 18 \text{ mm}^*\text{mrad}$.

Tune-shift mit der Amplitude

Fig.12: The tuneshift with amplitude of the DIFL lattice. With the actual amplitudes of smaller than 1 mm the tuneshift is relatively small.

Tune-shift mit der Energie

Fig.13: The tuneshift with energy deviations in %. The energy acceptance is better as 3 % which is a high value.

Storage ring parameters:

Diffraction Limited Light Source (DIFL)

General:

Achromat structure		MBA / TME
Number of achromats	C	12
Circumference (m)	α	404.3
Momentum compaction	I	$2.43 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Beam current (mA)	Σ	100
Beam energy (GeV)	ϵ_H	3.0
Nat. emittance (nm rad)	ϵ_{x0}	0.55
Coupling factor	$\epsilon_{y0}/\epsilon_{x0}$	0.01
Natural energy spread	σ_{E0}/E_0	$9 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Crit. photon energy (keV)	λ_c	5.6
Crit. wavelength (nm)		0.22

Optics:

Betatron tunes	Q_x/Q_y	37.59 / 13.73
Natural chromaticities	ξ_x/ξ_y	-76.0 / -37.5
Beam functions (m/rad)		
(a) Straight section	β_x/β_y	5.00 / 3.00
(b) Bending magnet	β_{x0}/β_{y0}	0.32 / 12.3
(c) Maximal	β_{max}/β_{min}	12.5 / 15.9
(d) Minimal	β_{min}/β_{max}	0.32 / 2.18
Dispersion (m)		
(a) Straight section	η_{sx}	0.00
(b) Bending magnet	η_{bx}	1.40
Source size		
(a) Straight section	σ_{x0}/σ_{y0}	53.0 / 4.10
cross-section (μm)	$\sigma'_{x0}/\sigma'_{y0}$	10.6 / 1.40
divergency (μrad)		
(b) Bending magnet	σ_{x0}/σ_{y0}	13.4 / 8.30
cross-section (μm)	$\sigma'_{x0}/\sigma'_{y0}$	42.0 / 0.68
divergency (μrad)		

Fig.14: layout of a diffraction limited light source with a twelvefold MBA symmetry.